

PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDES. A CONTRIBUTION TO THE STUDY OF
THE TRIAD -N·C·S-. PART XIV. MECHANISM OF
DESULPHURISATION

BY RAMCHANDRA SAHASRABUDHEY AND HANS KRALL

Dixon's discussion of thirty years ago no longer agrees with all the facts now known and more modern view is advanced

About the year 1869 A. W. Hofmann desulphurised certain thiocarbamides with mercuric oxide (*Ber.*, 1869, 2, 455, 600, 687). In the case of thiocarbamilide he expressed the change by the following equation :

Weith (*Ber.*, 1874, 7, 10) recognised the true nature of the change and showed that desulphurisation was dependent on the removal of the elements of hydrogen sulphide from a thiocarbamide. Later some more thiocarbamides were desulphurised by other workers (*vide J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 343 for the references) using lead or copper salts as desulphurising agents and the reaction came to be recognised as represented by the equation :

Then followed the more extensive researches on desulphurisation by Dixon (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1889, 55, 618; 1893, 63, 318) who like Weith considered that desulphurisation was a process which essentially consisted in the withdrawal of the elements of hydrogen sulphide from thiocarbamides. Dixon established the following conclusions :

- (i) All monosubstituted thiocarbamides are desulphurised.
- (ii) All disubstituted thiocarbamides, which contain at least one aryl substituent, are desulphurised.
- (iii) Disubstituted thiocarbamides, which contain both the substituents non-aromatic, are not desulphurised.
- (iv) Tri- and tetra-substituted thiocarbamides are not desulphurised.

On Weith's view it is at once apparent that tri- and tetra-substituted thiocarbamides cannot be desulphurised as they do not contain the two hydrogen atoms required for the removal of sulphur as H₂S. But so far any explanation of the rather unexpected behaviour of dialkyl thiocarbamides, which do not undergo desulphurisation, has been lacking. Dixon considered all thiocarbamides to have similar constitutions (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 2502). Obviously the easy desulphurisation of diaryl compounds in sharp contrast to the nondesulphurisability of dialkyl derivatives cannot be explained on any theory of the constitution of substituted thiocarbamides which assumes similar constitutions for both classes of compounds.

We think that any theory of desulphurisation of thiocarbamides should be consistent with the following observations :

- (i) Dialkyl substituted and tri- and tetra-substituted thiocarbamides do not undergo desulphurisation.

(ii) Desulphurisation does not take place in a strong acid medium. It occurs almost quantitatively in alkaline media and partially also in dilute solutions of weak acids. In concentrated solutions of weak acids it is suppressed (*vide*, Part XV of this series, p. 67).

(iii) Salts of such metals as copper, mercury, lead and silver only are effective in bringing about desulphurisation.

(iv) In contrast to the usual slowness of organic reactions in general, desulphurisation is quite a quick process and the impression that it is an ionic reaction is hard to avoid.

We suggest the following mechanism for desulphurisation :

The hydroxides of copper, mercury, lead and silver are known to be active desulphurising agents. Salts of weak acids of these metals (*e.g.* copper acetate) are also effective to a limited extent, but this property of these salts is probably a result of their easy hydrolysis into the corresponding hydroxides (*vide*, Part XV).

We think that the reaction is initiated by the formation of molecular compounds of thiocarbamides with the metallic bases through co-ordination at the sulphur atom. There is ample evidence for such co-ordination (*vide*, separate communication on the constitution of metal salt derivatives of thiocarbamides). Werner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1890, 57, 283) in his studies with the benzyl chloride derivatives of thiocarbamides showed that the S-substituted thiocarbamides yield complexes with metallic salts *e.g.*, those of platinum, mercury and gold, which decompose into such products as R. S. MX (where R is an alkyl group and MX, the metallic salt residue) and the sulphide of the metal. This explains why only the salts of the above metals are effective in bringing about desulphurisation.

Werner, Krall and others have shown that thiocarbamides tend to assume pseudothiocarbamidic configurations in aqueous solutions, thus :

A co-ordination complex of the metallic salt MX_2 or the hydroxide $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2$ with the thiocarbamide would therefore have the structures (I) and (II) :

If in the metallic salt or the hydroxide the valency force between the metal and the acid or hydroxide groups be weak, as is known to be the case with divalent mercury, lead and copper, the following changes become probable :

The mobility of a second hydrogen atom from *b*-nitrogen to sulphur in (III) makes it very

unstable and it rearranges in the following manner, a carbodiimide being formed along with the metallic sulphide and water.

If a second mobile hydrogen atom be not available in (IV), the hydrogens of the amino group in some way having been deprived of their mobility or if the residue MX is stable enough, decomposition of (IV) into (V) and (VI) may occur.

(V) through some mechanism not yet fully understood in cases where R is an aromatic radical, in presence of some oxidising agent, gets oxidised to thiodiazoles.

The salts of divalent copper, mercury etc. by virtue of their easy reducibility to the lower valency states themselves can serve the purpose of such oxidising agents in acidic media, the reduced salt residues combining with unchanged thiocarbamides to form various complexes (cf. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 25).

Silver nitrate is an effective desulphurising agent but it does not oxidise thiocarbamides probably because it cannot be reduced easily to a state of lower valency (cf. Lal and Krall, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 474) like the salts of divalent copper (cf. the reaction of CuCl with phenylthiocarbamide, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 25).

It is evident therefore from the above discussion that the mobility of a second hydrogen atom from nitrogen to sulphur is an essential condition for desulphurisation. This is supported, as already pointed out by the non-desulphurisability of the tri- and tetra-substituted thiocarbamides, whatever be the nature of their substituents. We consider that in acidic media desulphurisation is not possible because the mobility of the hydrogen of the amino or the imino group is checked through a process of salt formation which is very likely to occur under those conditions.

That such salt formation occurs has become sufficiently clear from our experiments with copper acetate and phenylthiocarbamide in strongly acidic boiling solutions where desulphurisation was found to be suppressed with increasing concentration of acetate ions in the medium (vide, Part XV). A large excess of acetate ions evidently increased the stability of the salt $\text{R}-\text{N} : \text{C}'\text{NH}_3^+\text{O}'\text{COCH}_3$, which in weaker acid concentrations would largely hydrolyse into

Action of nitrous acid in glacial acetic acid or strongly acidified solutions of phenylthiocarbamide supports the view stated above. It is found that under these conditions the amino group is not attacked but oxidation of phenylthiocarbamide

occurs, the nitroso derivative of Hector's base being obtained (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 33). In dilute acetic acid solutions, however, the amino group reacts with nitrous acid to form nitrogen (Mehta and Krall, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 640). The large excess of acetate ions in concentrated acetic acid solutions stabilises the ammonium salt of the acid and the amino group of the thiocarbanide. In a dilute solution, the salt $R^+N^+C^+NH_3O^-COCH_3$ is largely hydrolysed into free thiocarbanide and so the amino group

SH becomes exposed to the attack by the nitrous acid.

In a dilute solution of a strong acid the reaction follows the same course as in the concentrated solutions of weak acids. The explanation probably lies in the fact that even in dilute solutions the salts formed with strong acid are not hydrolysed into free thiocarbanide.

Nonesulphurisability of alkyl substituted thiocarbanides can also be explained on a similar reasoning. The alkyl radicals through their strongly proton attracting nature (+ π inductive effect) check the mobility of hydrogens from nitrogen to sulphur and hence no desulphurisation is possible. In a symmetrical compound the electronic displacements due to inductive effect can be shown as in (VII).

In a monoalkyl derivative or in a mixed disubstituted thiocarbanide the proton attracting effect of the alkyl group being either not strong enough to hinder the mobility of the hydrogens or having been partially neutralised by the - π effect of the aryl group, desulphurisation becomes possible.

In a diaryl thiocarbanide, on the other hand, the electronic displacements can be represented as in (VIII).

The - π effect of the aryl groups facilitates proton release from the -NH- group and the hydrogens of the imino groups can tautomerise on to the sulphur, this makes such compounds easily desulphurisable.

The scheme (VII) above requires as a direct consequence of the electron displacements towards the sulphur atom that in such alkyl thiocarbanides sulphur should become strongly negatively charged. A striking confirmation of this has been obtained by Lecher (*Annalen*, 1925, **445**, 35) who has shown that the sulphur atom of the tetramethylthiocarbamide can co-ordinate a proton in proton-donating media *viz.*, acidic solutions.

It has been pointed out in a preceding paragraph that desulphurisation is quite a quick process which suggests that ionic changes take place in the reaction. A tendency towards the segregation of the electrical charges in the different zones on the molecules as postulated by the above schemes and as has been found by Kumer and Fohjen (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 1944) from their study of dipole moments would make these molecules behave very nearly as ions.

A discussion of the other peculiarities in the behaviour of aliphatic thiocarbanides, which distinguish them from their aromatic congeners, will form the subject of a separate communication.